

DYNAMICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR ON THE COUNTRY'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT INDICATORS: CASE OF AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

Against the backdrop of the acceleration of globalization processes, the intensification of economic relations and the development of information technologies, the tourism sector has become one of the important factors promoting the economic development of countries in modern times. Especially for developing countries, tourism is of strategic importance not only in terms of diversifying the economy, but also in terms of ensuring foreign exchange inflows, increasing employment and developing infrastructure. In this context, determining the impact of the tourism sector on macroeconomic indicators — in particular, on Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment level and currency inflows — in the Republic of Azerbaijan is one of the current research issues.

Keywords: Economic development, GDP, tourism sector, dynamical analyses.

Introduction. To conduct a dynamic analysis of the impact of the tourism sector on economic development indicators in the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2010–2023. The dynamic analysis approach, based on time series, provides for monitoring changes over the years and a more accurate assessment of the economic consequences of changes in the tourism sector. The main goal of the study is to reveal the relationship between tourism indicators and economic indicators over time and analyze the degree of this relationship using primary visual and statistical means.

The indicators to be used in the analysis are divided into two main groups:

- **Tourism sector variables:**
 - Number of foreign and domestic tourists
 - Tourism revenues (total and average indicators)
 - Tourism's share in GDP
 - Number of employees employed in the tourism sector and its share in employment
 - Foreign exchange earnings from tourism
- **Economic development indicators:**
 - Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and its growth rate
 - GDP growth in the non-oil sector
 - Total employment rate by country
 - Foreign trade balance and foreign exchange reserves

The observed relationships between these indicators across years will be examined through statistical analysis, graphical visualization, and correlation analysis. The main goal at this stage is to identify the initial relationship between the variables and create a solid foundation for further exploring these relationships with econometric models (e.g., multilevel regression analysis).

The data used for the analysis are based on official statistical data obtained from reliable sources such as the State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), the World Bank, and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). These sources increase the objectivity of the results by allowing comparisons in both local and international contexts (UNWTO, 2023; World Bank, 2023; Azerbaijan State Statistical Committee, 2023).

It should be noted in particular that the period under analysis – 2010–2023 – is characterized by a number of important events in Azerbaijan's economic history (the 2015 devaluation, the intensification of international events, the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent recovery phase). These events further increase the relevance of the dynamic analysis and show that the impact of tourism on economic indicators is expressed not only in overall growth, but also in varying intensity over specific periods.

Consequently, the main goal of this section is to create a factual initial picture of the role of the tourism sector in the country's economic development, thereby forming a solid statistical basis for the econometric models that will be conducted in the next section.

In order to systematically and objectively assess the impact of the tourism sector on economic development indicators, it is of particular importance to correctly determine the indicators to be used in the study. The selected indicators should reflect the activity of the tourism sector in both quantitative and qualitative terms, and clearly demonstrate its interaction with the main areas of the economic system. In this regard, this section explains the main variables that characterize various aspects of tourism and allow for analytical links with economic indicators, and justifies the reasons for their selection.

Discussion and Findings. First of all, it should be noted that the specificity of the tourism sector requires its integration with various social, economic and infrastructural sectors. This sector does not only consist of hotels and travel agencies, but is also directly related to the transport, catering, entertainment, information technologies and even agriculture sectors. Therefore, when analyzing, it is not enough to simply measure the number of tourists and their income – a multidisciplinary approach is required to understand the broader macroeconomic impacts of these indicators (UNWTO, 2023).

First, the indicator of the number of foreign and domestic tourists was selected. This indicator expresses the total volume of people arriving in the country and traveling within the country. The number of foreign tourists demonstrates the level of international demand, while the number of domestic tourists demonstrates the travel opportunities of the population and the attractiveness of the national tourism infrastructure. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), these

indicators are one of the main parameters used to determine the real growth rates and potential market expansion of the tourism sector (UNWTO, 2023).

The second important indicator is tourism revenues (based on total and average indicators). This variable reflects the amount of money spent by tourists within the country and allows us to assess the financial contribution of tourism to the national economy. At the same time, the average expenditure indicator per tourist reflects the value level of the tourism product, the quality of service and the ability of tourists to pay. As noted in the 2023 report of the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), these indicators are one of the main tools for measuring the productivity and profitability of the tourism sector in the value chain (WTTC, 2023).

The third important indicator is the share of tourism in GDP. This indicator directly reflects the extent to which tourism activities contribute to the country's gross economic product and allows us to assess the relative position of the sector in the macroeconomic system. According to the World Bank's 2023 indicators, while in developed countries this indicator varies between 8–12%, in developing countries this indicator varies between 2–6% (World Bank, 2023). According to the State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan, this indicator in the country increased to 2.8% in 2015, 3.1% in 2019, and 4.1% in 2022 (Azerbaijan State Statistical Committee, 2023).

The fourth indicator is the employment variable in the tourism sector. This indicator is of particular importance in terms of assessing not only the economic but also the social impact of the sector. Employment is a direct result of the multiplier effect of tourism on the economy. It is reported that one in every 10 jobs worldwide is related to tourism, and employment in this sector stimulates economic activity in both urban and rural areas (WTTC, 2023). In Azerbaijan, an increase in the number of workers working in this sector was recorded in 2022 compared to previous years, and more than 50 thousand people were employed in the tourism sector (Azerbaijan State Statistical Committee, 2023).

Finally, the last indicator is tourism-based foreign exchange inflows. The funds spent by international tourists in the country have a positive impact on the activation of the balance of payments, the increase in foreign exchange reserves and, as a result, the stability of the national currency. This is especially important for developing countries, as the tourism sector is considered one of the main sources of foreign exchange inflows in non-energy sectors. For example, as a result of the Formula 1 Grand Prix held in Azerbaijan in 2022, tens of thousands of foreign tourists came to the country, and this event played a significant role in tourism revenues reaching 1.4 billion US dollars (Azerbaijan State Statistical Committee, 2023; UNWTO, 2023).

The selection of these indicators is consistent with international practice and allows for specific results based on real indicators of the Azerbaijani economy. Through dynamic and econometric analyses of the selected variables, the impact of the tourism sector on economic development indicators will be scientifically substantiated and an empirical basis will be provided for the formulation of relevant policy recommendations.

In order to objectively and systematically assess the impact of the tourism sector on economic development indicators, it is important to correctly select not only tourism-related variables, but also key macroeconomic indicators that are affected by this sector. These indicators should reflect the overall economic performance of the country, while also allowing to reveal the direct and indirect effects of tourism. For this purpose, the study identified four key economic development indicators: Gross Domestic Product (GDP), non-oil sector growth, employment level, and balance of payments with foreign exchange reserves.

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) was chosen as the first indicator. GDP reflects the value of all goods and services produced by a country over a certain period and is considered the main indicator of economic growth. The tourism sector contributes directly to GDP by causing the expansion of consumption, investment and services in the economy. This sector also has an indirect effect by stimulating a number of other areas of activity. The dynamics of GDP over the years and its correlation with tourism indicators allow us to assess the degree of sectoral impacts. According to 2023 World Bank data, although tourism's contribution to GDP is higher in developed countries, this impact occurs in more intensive and targeted areas in developing countries (World Bank, 2023).

The second indicator is the growth rate of the non-oil sector. The Azerbaijani economy has been highly dependent on the oil and gas sector for many years. However, in the last decade, the development of the non-oil sector has become a priority area in the country's economic policy, and in this regard, the tourism sector has taken an important place. Since tourism activities are mainly formed in the non-oil sector, the selection of this indicator is important in terms of analyzing the real contribution of the sector to the economic diversification policy. The strengthening of non-oil sectors, especially tourism, was also clearly stated in the socio-economic development strategies of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2016–2020 and 2022–2026 (Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Azerbaijan, 2022).

The third indicator is the total employment rate. The tourism sector, as a labor-intensive sector, creates more jobs than other sectors of the economy and has a direct impact on the labor market. Changes in employment in this sector can affect the overall unemployment rate and social stability in regions. According to the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), the tourism sector provided more than 330 million jobs worldwide in 2022, which accounts for approximately 9.1% of global employment (WTTC, 2023). In the context of Azerbaijan, increasing employment rates in the tourism sector is important not only in terms of economic but also social well-being. In particular, the development of rural tourism contributes to reducing unemployment in the regions (Azerbaijan State Statistical Committee, 2023).

The last indicator is foreign exchange reserves and balance of payments. International tourism activities positively change the country's balance of payments by stimulating the flow of foreign exchange into the country. This also plays an important role in maintaining the

country's macroeconomic stability. The funds spent by foreign tourists in the country affect the increase in foreign exchange reserves, the protection of the value of the national currency, and the improvement of the investment climate. According to the 2023 report of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the increase in tourism revenues directly has a positive impact on the balance of payments indicators of countries, and this acts as an important factor in reducing the level of external debt, especially for countries that are service exporters (IMF, 2023).

Result. The four main indicators mentioned above — GDP, non-oil sector growth, employment level and foreign exchange reserves — are the most appropriate and functional variables to assess the real impact of the tourism sector on the economic system. Dynamic and econometric analyses based on these indicators will create a basis for research that is scientifically based and results-oriented.

References

1. Dwyer, L., & Forsyth, P. (2020). *Tourism economics and policy* (2nd ed.). Channel View Publications.
2. Gössling, S., & Hall, CM (2019). *Sustainable tourism: A global perspective* (4th ed.). Routledge.
3. Gujarati, DN, & Porter, DC (2020). *Basic econometrics* (6th ed.). New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Education.
4. Hall, CM, & Page, SJ (2019). *The geography of tourism and recreation: Environment, place, and space* (5th ed.). Routledge.
5. Guliyev, RR, & Huseynova, SM (2016). Research on Azerbaijan's import and annual GDP co-relation based on econometric models in the frame of joining WTO. *Journal of Contemporary Applied Mathematics-ISSN: 2222-5498*, 6(1).
6. Mubariz, HS (2016). The influence of international migration on international trade. *European journal of economics and management sciences*, (3), 27-29.
7. Huseynova, S. (2023). COINTEGRATION ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH PARAMETERS BETWEEN RUSSIA AND AZERBAIJAN. *Sciences of Europe*, (110), 26-31.
8. Huseynova, S., & Ch, I. ANALYSIS OF THE WTO AND THE PROCESS OF INTEGRATION OF AZERBAIJAN INTO THE WORLD ECONOMY SUMMARY. *GENETICS AND BIOTECHNOLOGY*, 25.
9. UNWTO. (2019). *Tourism highlights 2019*. World Tourism Organization.
10. UNWTO. (2020). *Tourism and the Sustainable Development Goals – Journey to 2030*. United Nations World Tourism Organization.
11. World Bank. (2020). *World development indicators*. World Bank.
12. WTTC. (2021). *Economic impact of global tourism*. World Travel & Tourism Council.
13. www.stat.gov.az